

ANALYZING WEBSITE DATA TO ENHANCE E-COMMERCE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The paper aims to define the website analytics in e-retailing industry. Most customers prefer to buy online rather than buy in a traditional way. Most business transfer and adapt their strategies to e-commerce channels. The research is about the websites analytics of four e-retailing giants Amazon and Walmart. The results shown that how many traffic they use, marketing channels engagement and displaying advertisement. Based on the obtained results, a set of recommendations was proposed to increase the loyalty of Internet consumers.

Key words: *e-commerce, website analytics, digital marketing*

Introduction

In the digital world, having a strong online activeness, particular website can help to increase the productivity and revenue of any business. Nowadays consumers do an online search before purchasing some products of the company. Plus, it is great chance to show up what business is and establish the brand awareness among customers. A strong built website makes the business apart from its competitors as well.

In this paper the four giant companies Amazon, Walmart's websites are analyzed and compared by the web analysis tools. A good website analysis says how the company's sites support their goals in the future. The current work addresses these companies' website analysis in the metrics of traffics, engagement, geography, marketing channels and displaying ads. Based on the findings of the research, some specific recommendations that refer to the company's objectives are given in concluding part.

Company overview

Amazon.com

The giant e-retailing business, Amazon.com was founded in 1993 by Jeff Bezos in USA. Initially it was online bookshop. During the 7 years they could not make a profit, they had to change its corporate-level strategy into acquisitions and mergers approach (Landrecht et al, 2020). Today Amazon become a customer paradise that they can buy anything online. They did a success by understanding and implementing the power of technological progress. Currently amazon offers more than 40 categories products including clothes, electronics, food, books, home appliances.

The consumers of Amazon satisfied with its low prices, convenience, wide range of selection and availability at any time. The recipe of its success based on consonant value chain reinvention, development of digitalization and implementation of modern payment methods. Plus, its acquisition in improving its products and service make Amazon leading e-retailing in international market (Filson, 2004).

Financial status of Amazon is really satisfactory, it shows 386,1 billion sales revenue (Annual Report, December. 2020). Compared to 2019, it grows 38 % from 280,5 billion. By innovating new products and services on low price, best available selection and convenient way, Amazon holds its position as a retail giant in competitive market.

Walmart

Walmart is dominant offline retail in the US market with \$524 billion in 2020 (Annual Report, 2020). It entered the market as offline retailing in, it has taken steps to increase its presence in e-retailing. By integrating new channels to generate orders online, Walmart did a great job in e-retailing as well.

The mission of the company is “to save people money so they can live better”. Walmart’s success in its simple foundation “Every Day Low Price” by offering great merchandise (Walmart.com, 2020). Walmart works directly with supplier in order to offer low prices to their customers. By bringing together offline, it builds customers loyalty and trust in best online capabilities too.

Walmart’s another key factor in its success is great controlling over supply chain. It makes Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) with suppliers for cutting the costs (Marcilla, 2014).

From the beginnings of its history (1962), Walmart has been continuing to grow and expand internationally. It has 10,500 stores in 24 countries and Walmart.com website in order to operating and offering best service in speedy growing market.

The analysis of metrics on the companies’ websites

Website analytics is the important for providing the insight and data that useful for creating best user experience. It is a tool for the collection, measurement and reporting of the website of the company (Burby and Brown, 2007). Today website analysis is used in many purposes such as traffic monitoring, optimization of e-commerce, marketing, improving website performance and web-based campaigns. By analyzing these categories, the companies improve their website design (website information architecture, navigation, content layout, users’ interaction). Plus, it helps to understand and identify the users’ interest and attention areas. The another reason of conducting web analysis is optimizing e-commerce (Zheng and Peltsverger, 2015). Most companies use the website analysis for understanding their customers’ need to increase their traffic and revenue. the other benefits from the website analysis are the followings:

- ✓ Improving e-CRM on customer orientation and retention
- ✓ Measurement of actions success (e.g. commercial campaigns)
- ✓ Identifying problems
- ✓ Improving web applications of the business as well

In order to analyze the website of the company and relate to its objectives, the meaningful and measurable metrics should be used. The most traditional used metrics are visit count (page view, unique visitor), visit duration (time on page and site), bounce rate and exit rate (Kaushik, 2009). These metrics identify how often the visitors are on the site, what is the duration of the visit, how many pages are visited every session.

Based on the data of Similarweb.com., the main features of website analysis of four companies (Amazon, Walmart) are identified and described below:

Traffic and engagement. This metrics says about the traffic of websites such as number of visits, engagement, rankings (Similar web, 2021). The insights of the traffics are total visits,

device distribution, global rank, country rank and category rank. Engagement key metrics show are the followings:

- ✓ *Monthly visits* sum all visits every month. It is essential to know about the overall size of the companies
- ✓ *Monthly unique visitors* identify the average amount of individual visits
- ✓ *Visits* are the total amount of visitors in particular period
- ✓ *Visit duration* is visitors spending time on the website (in hours, minutes, seconds)
- ✓ *Pages/ Visits:* the number of the pages that visited in particular time period
- ✓ *Bounce rate* shows the website visitors' percentage after leaving one page. It identifies how the company's website retains the visitors.

(fig 1)

Geography shows the percentages of sending traffics and total traffic share each analyzed companies in top 5 countries. This metrics helps to business in focusing on particular country in high rate. Countries with low number should not be putted effort too much. The graph (fig 3) below reveals the highly stood countries in the list. The giant portion of the traffic share is marked in the USA with 79,42 %. The percentage of Canada, India and United Kingdom are small but noteworthy.

(fig 3)

Marketing Channels are the metric that used analyzing the overview of channels that upcoming traffics. The key metrics are described below:

- **Direct.** This is the tool that identifies traffic entering directly to the website. It is considered to be barometer of the brand awareness

- Email. This traffic metrics show how the company's customers loyalty engaged through their own mails.
- Referrals. This metric measures the business' strong strategy and media coverage.
- Social. The loyal community of customers are the base of this metric. (Facebook, Instagram, etc)

Recommendations

The results based on the web analysis conducted on four e-retailing companies are accepted and applied in recommendation part. The comparison of results of these metrics point out that the companies have some advantages among competitors. On the other hand, their websites have some shortages in a particular traffics.

Bounce rate. Walmart should lower their bounce rate. It is advised to work on their style. Consumers prefer highly readable sites rather than more buttons. It is more attractive having clear and easy buttons for customers. It is likely to bounce the website if your clients do not understand your products.

Social channels. It is recorded low numbers of total traffics of social platforms in channel overview for each company. Even Amazon's social platform presence shows less traffics of total share. Most customers, especially youngster's usage of SMs are higher in our digital world. Is is highly recommended to improve their activeness on social networks.

Moreover, it is suggested to improve the websites loading time in order to increase the traffics and satisfaction of customers

Conclusion

The conclusion based on the outcomes of theoretical overview and results of practical research is that the website analysis metrics are the statistical indicators of website actions. The four companies' websites are analyzed and compared in the second part. All data were viewed and clear suggestions are recommended for the companies' websites. Successful implementation of the metrics support customer satisfaction on the web of the business.

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